

Polydentate Carboxamide Ligands as Analytical Reagents[†]

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Biphenyl bridged, binucleating and polydentate macromolecular ligand series, H_2L , possessing two terminal $-NH-CO-A-COOH$, carboxamide moieties (where $A = -CH_2-CH_2-$ or $-CH=CH-$ or *ortho*-phenylene linkage), has been synthesised and was found to be a set of potential analytical reagents as H_2L suspensions for conductometric and pH-metric aqueous acid-base titrations on one hand and as Na_2L aqueous solutions for gravimetric analysis of several bivalent metal ions on the other. Due to the large separation between the two carboxamide coordinating moieties, only Na_2L formation at any mixing of NaOH and H_2L and only one wave in the pH-metric titration of H_2L suspension against a standard NaOH, were observed. Further, the solutions of Na_2L were found to be satisfactory turbidimetric reagents for Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , La^{III} and UO_2^{II} ions in the concentration range $10^{-5} - 10^{-3}M$.

Organic compounds possessing carboxamide, $-NH-CO-A-COOH$ functional set, where A is an ethylenic or *ortho*-phenylene linkage moiety, have been reported to have noteworthy fungicidal character¹. Further, they have been found to be potential coordinating centres yielding complexes of diverse physico-chemical properties^{2,3}. Very recently the present authors have reported³ the characterisation of $(M_2L_2 \cdot H_2O)_n$ type polymeric coordination compounds (2), where H_2L is a biphenyl bridged carboxamide ligand (1). The large separation between the two terminal carboxamide moieties, the strong chelating potential of the carboxamide groups, the high molecular weight of the H_2L ligands (1), the near insolubility of the chelates (2) but high solubility as Na_2L salts and the diversity with which a series of H_2L ligands

could be synthesised, have led the authors to investigate the analytical capabilities of these H_2L ligand series, the results of which are presented here.

Results and Discussion

Conductometric titration of H_2L against strong and weak bases: The ligands H_2L are useful as weak dibasic acid volumetric reagents to determine the strength of dilute strong and weak bases such as NaOH, KOH and NH_4OH , conductometrically.

H_2L (~1 mmol) was suspended in water (40 ml) and titrated conductometrically against a standard 0.2M base. The results are collected in Table 1. The calculated and observed end-points agreed well within the experimental limits. Since the H_2L is a weighed-out suspension, statistical treatment was done only for five trials of dadpm-male ligand with NaOH.

Using the conductometric method, the free energy of dissociation of each of these carboxamide systems was evaluated. The method is described as follows. The equivalent conductances of any given Na_2L solutions of five different concentrations were measured. Then the equivalent conductance was plotted against square-root of the concentration. Internal extrapolation of the least-square fit straight line to Y-axis gave the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution. Using Kohlrausch's law of independent migration of ions and the equivalent conductances at infinite dilution of Na^+ and H^+ , the equivalent conductances (Λ_0) of H_2L were evaluated. Employing the relation,

$$\Lambda_0 \approx \frac{1000 k}{s} \quad (1)$$

where k is the specific conductance of the aqueous suspension of H_2L , s , the solubility in g-eq. wt per litre was calculated. As these H_2L 's are very

1 (H_2L)

Z	X	Anhydride	Row combination labelled as
CH_3	H	Maleic	dadpm-male
-	H	Succinic	benzi-succi
-	CH_3	Phthalic	<i>o</i> -tol-i-phthal
OCH_3		Maleic	<i>o</i> -diani-male
		and so on	

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D=H₂O for M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}
D does not exist for M=Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}

TABLE 1—END-POINTS* FROM THE CONDUCTOMETRIC AND pH-METRIC TITRATIONS

Sl. no.	Titrand	Titrants				
		NaOH		KOH		NH ₄ OH
		Cond.	pH	Cond.	pH	Cond.
1.	dadpm-male	10.15 (10.10)	9.99 (9.90)	12.00 (12.08)	7.95 (8.03)	9.95 (9.98)
2.	dadpm-phthal	10.20 (10.16)	12.50 (12.61)	8.95 (9.06)	9.90 (9.91)	10.05 (10.13)
3.	dadpm-succi	8.95 (9.02)	13.90 (13.99)	9.45 (9.52)	10.25 (10.30)	8.85 (9.02)
4.	benzi-male	8.80 (8.87)	8.00 (8.20)	8.75 (8.83)	8.65 (8.66)	9.00 (9.08)
5.	<i>o</i> -toli-male	9.90 (9.98)	7.95 (8.03)	6.30 (6.35)	10.35 (10.37)	7.80 (7.93)
6.	<i>o</i> -dianisi-male	10.05 (10.13)	8.80 (8.87)	10.35 (10.41)		

*In millilitres with values in parentheses as calculated volumes.

sparingly soluble, adoption of equation (1) is justified. The *s* values were converted into molarities (*M*) and by substituting the latter in

$$K_a = 4M^3 \quad (2)$$

the acid dissociation constant (*K_a*) was evaluated. The standard free energy of dissociation was then calculated using the thermodynamic relationship,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_a \quad (3)$$

The values of specific conductances (*k*) of H₂L aqueous suspensions, *A*₀, *K_a*, *pK_a* and ΔG° are collected in Table 2. It is interesting to note that the trends in the *pK_a* values of these carboxyamides are similar to those in other organic carboxylic acids, e.g. compare the *pK_a*'s of dadpm-succi (11.58), dadpm-male (11.54) and dadpm-phthal (11.02) to those of propionic acid (4.87), acrylic acid (4.26) and benzoic acid (4.21) respectively.

pH-metric titration of H₂L against strong bases: The H₂L systems are found to be useful analytical reagents in pH-metric titration also in order to determine the strength of strong bases. The pH-metric data are collected in Table 1.

The acid dissociation constant (*K_a*) and the corresponding *pK_a* values were calculated by way of

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE, pH AND THERMODYNAMIC DATA

Sl. no.	H ₂ L	pH ^a	<i>k</i> ^b	<i>A</i> ₀ ^c	<i>K_a</i> ^{d,e}	<i>pK_a</i> ^e	ΔG° ^f
1.	dadpm-succi	4.33	1.29	402.85	2.63 (2.88)	11.58 (11.54)	15.89
2.	dadpm-male	3.98	1.35	435.00	4.091 (4.67)	11.39 (11.33)	15.63
3.	dadpm-phthal	3.76	1.45	441.24	9.54 (10.23)	11.02 (10.99)	15.13
4.	benzi male	4.02	1.18	432.56	2.88 (3.38)	11.54 (11.47)	15.84
5.	<i>o</i> -toli-male	4.23	1.14	427.74	1.65 (1.99)	11.78 (11.70)	16.17
6.	<i>o</i> -dianisi-male	3.99	1.33	430.89	3.63 (4.17)	11.44 (11.38)	15.70

^aMeasured for the suspension at 27°. ^bMeasured for the suspension at 27° in Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹; ^cIn Ω⁻¹ cm² (g eq wt)⁻¹. ^dIn mol³ dm⁻³ at 27°. ^eValues in parentheses are those obtained from pH-metric titration. ^fIn kcal mol⁻¹.

the pH-metric titration. The method is described below.

The ionisation of the H_2L is considered as

based on the single wave in pH-metric titration and the highly poor solubility of H_2L . It follows from equation (4) that

$$pK_a = 2 \text{ pH} - \log [L^{2-}] \quad (4)$$

The pH of the pH-metric titration mixture was measured at an arbitrary point (burette reading) before the end-point and substituted in equation (5) along with the concentration of L^{2-} formed, by that point, to evaluate the pK_a and K_a . The pK_a and K_a , obtained in this method, are collected in Table 2. The pH of the suspensions of these carboxy amide ligands are also given in Table 2.

Gravimetric analysis of bivalent metal ions with Na_2L : The ligands, H_2L are soluble in basic media yielding Na_2L solutions. The bivalent L^{2-} anions are potential tetradentate binucleating ligands. If a warm aqueous solution of bivalent metal ion M^{II} ($M^{II} = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}$) is mixed with that of L^{2-} in equimolar fashion, precipitates are immediately and quantitatively formed³. The high degree quantitative precipitation of M^{II} by L^{2-} and the fact that L^{2-} has large molecular weight, render Na_2L solutions as potential gravimetric reagents for several bivalent metal ions in the concentration range $10^{-1} - 10^{-4} M$.

The data obtained from the gravimetric analysis are collected in Table 3. It is already reported³ that the metal complexes confirm to the structure 2. The formula weights shown in Table 3 have

TABLE 3—GRAVIMETRIC ANALYTICAL DATA^a

Sl. no.	Na_2L solution of	Metal Ion		
		Cu^{II} (CuL) ₂ ^b	Co^{II} ($CoL \cdot 2H_2O$) ₂	Ni^{II} ($NiL \cdot 2H_2O$) ₂
1.	dadpm-male	911.61 ^c	974.46	974.01
		25.50 ^d	23.61	23.51
		25.65 ^e	23.45	23.45
		(25.41) ^f	(23.57)	(23.48)
2.	o-toli-phthal	140.10	1266.49	1266.05
		25.84	23.71	23.61
		25.74	23.65	23.55
		(25.41)	(23.57)	(23.48)
3.	o-dianisi-male	1003.87	1094.76	1094.31
		25.78	23.65	23.56
		25.62	23.54	23.68
		(25.41)	(23.57)	(23.48)

^aAll the gravimetric data in mg. ^bFormula of the repeating unit of the polymer structure (2). ^cFormula weight of the repeating unit. ^dMeasured mass of M^{II} ion as ($ML \times H_2O$) precipitated by 40 ml of 0.01M ($x=0$ for Cu^{II} , $x=2$ for Co^{II} and Ni^{II}) of Na_2L solutions. ^eMeasured mass of M^{II} ion in a parallel analysis (Cu^{II} by photometry as tetraamminecopper(II) sulphate at 612 nm, Co^{II} by gravimetry as tetrapyridinecobalt(III) dithiocyanate and Ni^{II} by gravimetry as bis-dimethylglyoximatecopper(II)). ^fExpected mass of M^{II} ion in (d) and (e).

been considered along with structures 1 and 2 for calculating the amount of M precipitated and the same was compared with the value observed from the photometry or conventional gravimetry⁴, which are parallelly performed.

Turbidimetric analysis of various metal ions using Na_2L : The Na_2L solutions render turbidity at ambient temperatures with various metal ions in the concentration range $10^{-6} - 10^{-3} M$. In a typical experiment, a constant $10^{-3} M$ concentration of Na_2L is maintained in a series of five 25 ml volumetric flasks through which the metal ion concentration is varied within $10^{-4} M$. The resulting turbidity is corrected for the background and found to be linear with the metal ion concentration. Further, it is noted that the turbidity is stable and does not coagulate till 95° . A few representative turbidimetric calibration plots are shown in Fig. 1 from

Fig. 1. Turbidimetric calibration plots, turbidity vs concentration of (a) Cu^{II} as the metal ion for various turbidimetric reagents, Na_2L , kept at a constant $10^{-3} M$; (●) o-dianisi male, (○) o-toli male, (Δ) dadpm male. (b) Turbidity vs metal ion concentration for various metal ions for a fixed $10^{-3} M$ of o-dianisi-male; (Δ) Th^{II} , (□) UO_2^{II} , (●) La^{III} , (◁) Co^{II} , (○) Cu^{II} , (x) Ni^{II} .

TABLE 4—TURBIDIMETRIC DATA*

Sl. no.	Na ₂ L solution of	Cu ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	UO ₂ ^{II}	Th ^{III}	La ^{III}
1.	dadpm-male	24.90 (25.00)	30.00 (29.90)	25.00 (29.85)	25.00 (24.80)	30.00 (29.85)	25.00 (25.00)
2.	<i>o</i> -dianisi-male	29.95 (30.00)	30.00 (29.95)	25.00 (24.85)	25.00 (24.90)	30.00 (29.95)	25.00 (24.95)
3.	<i>o</i> -toli-male	24.90 (25.00)	30.00 (29.80)	25.00 (24.90)	25.00 (25.00)	30.00 (29.80)	30.00 (29.95)

*All the values are expressed in molarities $\times 10^5$ with expected values in parentheses.

which a set of 'unknown' metal solutions are determined. The data thus obtained are collected in Table 4.

Experimental

Photometric analysis was carried out on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer. An Elico LI-120 pH-meter and a Systronics 305 conductivity bridge were used. Solutions were prepared using analytical grade reagents in double-distilled water. Measurements were done by thermostating the solutions.

The ligands, H₂L (1), were synthesised by mixing hot benzene solutions of any (substituted) benzidine such as 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl (benzidine) or 3,3'-dimethyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl (*o*-tolidine) or 3,3'-dimethoxy-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl (*o*-dianisidine) with that of any cyclic anhydride such as succinic anhydride or phthalic anhydride or maleic anhydride in a 1 : 2 molar ratio. The resulting solids (white from succinic and phthalic anhydrides or light yellow from maleic anhydride) were washed with hot benzene followed by acetone and dried under reduced pressure at 90°.

The standard solutions of Na₂L were prepared

by suspending H₂L (typically slightly above 0.025 mol) in water (50 ml) followed by dropwise addition of calculated volume of 0.4M NaOH solution while stirring. The volume of the solution was made up to 250 ml and adjusted to give exactly 0.1M Na₂L.

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References

1. R. S. BAICHWAL, R. M. BOXTER S. I. KANDEL and G. C. WALKER, *Can. J. Biochem. Physiol.*, 1960, **38**, 254; H. TRIPATHI, D. G. PRADHAN, B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1973, **37**, 1375.
2. K. N. RAYMOND and C. J. CARRANO, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1979, **12**, 183; H. SIGEL and R. B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 385; V. RAVINDAR, S. J. SWAMI, S. SRIHARI and P. LINGAIAH, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 1511; V. RAVINDAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, 1983.
3. T. SAROJINI and A. RAMACHANDRAIAH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 1174.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., E.L.B.S., London, 1962.